

VALUES INTEGRATION IN TEACHING DIFFERENT SUBJECTS IN PUBLIC SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN PILILLA, RIZAL: BASIS FOR ACTION PLAN DEVELOPMENT

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ABSTRACT

The study aims to determine the level of effectiveness of values integration in teaching the different subjects in public secondary schools in Pililla, Rizal. Descriptive research design was applied utilizing a questionnaire checklist to determine the level of effectiveness of values integration in teaching the different subjects with respect to classroom management, delivery of lesson, learning application, and learning assessment and personal traits. The questionnaire checklist was administered after permission to conduct the study was granted. The data were tallied, tabulated, analyzed and interpreted. The study concluded that perception of the teacher-respondents on the level of effectiveness of values integration in teaching different subjects differ significantly in terms of age, length of service, and subjects handled. On the other hand, sex, educational attainment and position title are not significant.

Keywords: *Quantitative, Values Integration, Public Secondary Schools, Rizal*

INTRODUCTION

Education is already a part man`s life. Education and man coexist because man learns as he continues to live and live as he continues to learn. It only becomes complicated by

the fact that there is no clear consensus about what is important about being and becoming educated.

Moreover, education is the primary agent of transformation towards sustainable development. Furthermore, it is regarded as the single potent factor that leads to the improvement of the individual as well as the society. As provided in Article XIV, section 1 of the 1987 Philippines Constitution: “The state shall protect and promote the right of all citizens to quality education at all levels and shall take appropriate steps to make such education accessible to all.”

The goal of Philippine Education is academic excellence, work experience efficiency and values internalization. Thus, the Philippine educational system is mandated to contribute to the maximum attainment of national development and unity with the framework based on a free and democratic system.

Values are behind all human goals. They are linked with the basic human needs. They emerge in the course of time through one’s exposure to people and different life conditions. One may be conscious of one’s values, reflecting on them regularly or one may be driven by unexpressed and unconscious desires. An individual may be motivated by undertakings that offer short term benefits or driven by momentary desires.

In recognition of this important role of the school in the society, Article XIV Section 3.2 of the 1987 Philippine Constitution states that: “All educational institutions shall inculcate patriotism and nationalism, foster love of humanity, respect for human rights; appreciation of the role of national heroes in the historical development of the country, teach the rights and duties of citizenship, strengthen ethical and spiritual values, develop oral character and personal discipline, encourage critical and creative thinking, broaden scientific and technological knowledge and promote vocational efficiency. This stressed that the educational thrusts of the Philippine Educational System are designed to update the school curricula and incorporate Filipino values that would adapt in the light of on-going changes, to the present needs and demands involving social and economic transformation and nation-building and relevance to the world of work.

In recent research on classroom management, Nie and Lau (2009) explored the differential associations of care and behavioral control with various student outcomes. Their study utilized a large sample of 3,196 Grade 9 students from 117 classes in Singapore to examine these relationships. Through hierarchical linear modeling, they found that both care and behavioral control were positively related to student engagement, even when controlling for gender and socioeconomic status. Moreover, while behavioral control negatively predicted classroom misbehavior, care positively predicted students’ satisfaction with school. These findings suggest that an effective classroom management strategy should integrate both care and behavioral control to enhance student engagement, reduce misbehavior, and increase satisfaction with school. This aligns with the self-determination theory, highlighting the importance of addressing both the emotional and behavioral needs of students in achieving multiple classroom management goals (Nie & Lau, 2009).

In navigating the complexities of our educational system, it's crucial to acknowledge the intrinsic relationship between education and values, as highlighted by Gray (2010). Instead of assigning blame for issues that arise, Gray advocates for a proactive approach, emphasizing the importance of recognizing, addressing, and resolving problems. Central to this approach is the implementation of Character Education in Schools, which Gray argues is essential for combating the crisis of character within our educational institutions. By integrating moral teachings into the curriculum and fostering collaboration among stakeholders, including parents, legislators, communities, media, and the educational system, character education programs can instill values that promote responsible citizenship and moral development among students, thus paving the way for a more ethically grounded society.

As mentioned in the K to 12 Philippine Basic Education Curriculum Framework is crafted to cater to the multifaceted needs of both the local and global community, with a primary focus on key aspects: poverty alleviation and holistic human development, moral fortification, cultivation of national identity, cultivation of productive citizenship, environmental sustainability, and global collaboration. It endeavors to empower individuals through quality education, aiming to diminish poverty and foster comprehensive human growth. Emphasizing the infusion of moral values and ethical principles, it aims to build a foundation of character and integrity in learners. Additionally, it aspires to instill a profound sense of national pride, identity, and love for the country, fostering a strong nationalistic spirit. Moreover, it seeks to equip students with the requisite knowledge, skills, and values to actively engage in nation-building and contribute positively to society. By integrating environmental education and advocating for global partnerships, it seeks to promote responsible environmental stewardship and foster collaboration with the global community to address mutual challenges and achieve shared progress. In essence, the K to 12 curriculum framework endeavors to cultivate well-rounded individuals who are not only academically proficient but also socially responsible and globally conscious citizens (Ocampo, 2014).

Incorporating character education into the core academic curriculum is a pivotal aspect of successful character education programs. While many programs assert integration, they often merely insert character lessons between academic subjects. However, Berkowitz (2012) advocates for a deeper integration by leveraging existing character content within academic curricula. This approach involves mining the character-related themes inherent in subjects like language arts and social studies and seamlessly integrating character-based lessons into these academic domains. For instance, programs like the Child Development Project and Facing History and Ourselves offer models of integration, with the former featuring a multicultural literature curriculum and the latter focusing on historical genocide within its history curriculum. By intertwining character content with academic lessons and employing character-building methods, educators can foster a more holistic approach to character education that permeates throughout the academic experience.

According to Thornberg and Oğuz (2013), values education primarily focuses on adherence to societal values and norms, with an emphasis on how to treat others and

self-responsibility. The study found that teachers typically did not adopt a critical approach, instead highlighting their role as good models in daily interactions with students. Values education was described as an integral part of everyday social interactions using common language, and there was a noted lack of professional knowledge in this domain among teachers.

According to Pala (2011) character education can be initiated at any grade level. It is important to set a strong foundation during the earlier grades and to reinforce and build upon that foundation during the later grades. To be effective, character education must include the entire school community and must be infused throughout the entire school curriculum and culture. He concluded in his study that the development of socialization skills and integration of character education are an important part of a child's academic success. Character education efforts may be effective when implemented rigorously and with a scientific foundation. Schools should focus on teaching character within the regular curriculum.

Moreso, the increasing political, social, and scientific focus on the moral aspects of teaching extends to teacher education. Willemse, Lunenberg, and Korthagen (2005) present an exploratory study on preparing student teachers for moral education. They describe the design of goals, program components, and teaching and learning methods for a segment of the first-year curriculum at a primary education teacher training institute. The study involved feedback from teacher educators who implemented the curriculum and student teachers who participated in it, assessing whether they recognized the intended moral aspects. Additionally, the study measured the curriculum's impact on student teachers' learning through pre- and post-tests. The findings suggest a need for greater emphasis on the implicit and unplanned aspects of preparing student teachers for moral education.

A study by Benninga (2003) entitled "The Relationship of Character education Implementation and Academic Achievement in Elementary Schools," was a large study including data from 651 schools. The results indicate that a composite summary score of character education criteria is positively correlated with academic indicators across years. The elementary schools in the sample with solid character education programs defined by our six criteria and their eleven indicators not only show positive relationships with academic indicators that same year, but also evidence positive correlations across the next two academic years. The cited study is related to the present study as it focused on character education and its relationship to academic performance which is the same focus as that of the present study.

The DepEd Values Education Program gears mainly in translating values from the abstract into practical. The importance behind this program is that when values are subjected into a book or in a classroom seem to be in abstract way, but its effectiveness is said to be true when such values are transmitted to real life. In public secondary schools' values education is integrated in teaching the different subjects. Integration of values education in the different subjects depends for its success on the teacher's creativity in making use of the situation to facilitate the student's values development. In

the study of Kariuki and Williams (2006) examined the correlation between character traits and academic performance among AFJROTC cadets, utilizing a sample of 20 male and 20 female cadets from Sullivan South High School. Their research revealed a significant positive relationship between character traits, particularly moral behavior, and academic performance as measured by grade point average. These findings align with current literature suggesting that character education programs can positively influence both behavior and academic outcomes among students in similar educational contexts. Understanding the impact of character traits on academic performance underscores the importance of integrating character education into school curricula to foster holistic student development and improve educational outcomes.

As England (2009) found out in his study that character education is an important element that must be included in California K12 public schools to increase student achievement and facilitate a safe and effective learning environment. He concluded that when implementing character education, program elements should be studied to obtain the desired outcome wanted from the program. Hence teachers need to be trained or re-trained. Thus, the researcher conceived this study to determine the effectiveness of values integration in teaching the different subject.

Research Questions

The general research question that this study attempts to address is the effectiveness of values integration in teaching the different subjects in public secondary schools in Pililla, Rizal.

1. What is the profile of the teacher-respondents in terms of: Age, sex, educational attainment, length of service, position title, and subjects handled?
- 2: What is the level of effectiveness of values integration in teaching the different subjects with respect to classroom management, delivery of lessons, learning application, learning assessment and personal traits.
- 3: Is there a significant difference in the perception of the respondents on the level of effectiveness of values integration in teaching the different subjects with respect to the different aspects in terms of their profile?
- 4: What action plan may be proposed to enhance the values integration in teaching the different subjects?

METHODOLOGY

This quantitative research employed a descriptive survey approach using a questionnaire checklist developed by the researcher to evaluate the integration of values in teaching different subjects. The study was conducted in public secondary schools in Pililla, Rizal, including Bugarin National High School, Hulo National High School, Malaya National High School, Pililla National High School, and Quisao National High School in School Year 2014-2015. The respondents comprised 161 teachers from these five public secondary schools, determined through a stratified sampling method.

The questionnaire checklist consisted of two parts: the first part dealt with the personal profile of the respondents, and the second part focused on various aspects of the effectiveness of values integration in teaching different subjects. Each aspect included 10 items. Respondents rated each item on a scale of 1-5, with 1 indicating "Not effective" and 5 indicating "Very Much Effective." The questionnaire was pretested with 15 teachers from Tanay National High School, yielding an r-value of .83, indicating that the instrument is both valid and reliable.

To interpret the data gathered, several statistical tools were applied. Frequency and percentage distribution were used to determine the profile of the respondents. The weighted mean was employed to assess the perception of respondents on the effectiveness of values integration in teaching different subjects. Additionally, one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used to determine significant differences in perceptions based on the respondents' profiles.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 presents the frequency and percentage distribution of the teacher-respondents in terms of the selected variable.

Table 1
Frequency and Percentage Distribution of the Teacher-Respondents in Terms of the Selected Variables

AGE	f	%
50 years old and above	29	18
40-49	48	30
30-39	39	24
29 years and below	45	28
Total	161	100

SEX	f	%
Male	38	24
Female	123	76
Total	161	100
Educational Attainment	f	%
Pd.D./Ed. D units	2	1
MA Graduate	28	17
With MA units	91	57
Bachelor's Degree	40	25
Total	161	100
Length of Service	f	%
30 years and above	39	24
20-29	48	30
10-19	45	28
9 years and below	29	18
Total	161	100
Position Title	f	%
Master Teacher I	5	3
Teacher III	23	14
Teacher II	39	24
Teacher I	94	59
Total	161	100
Subjects Handled	f	%
English	34	21
Science	47	29
TLE	36	22
Mapeh	44	27
Mathematics	47	29
Filipino	48	30
Araling Panlipunan	48	17
Edukasyon sa Pagpapakatao	36	22

As shown in table 1, out of 161 teacher respondents, 30 percent are ages 40-49 years old, 28 percent are ages 29 years old and below, 24 percent are ages 30-39 years old, and the rest have ages 50 years old and above. In terms of sex, most of the respondents are female with 123 or 76 percent out of 161 teacher respondents. With regards to their educational attainment, the majority are pursuing graduate education with 57 percent having earned units in master's degree and 1 percent have doctoral units. Only 25 percent have not earned units in graduate education. In terms of length of service, most of the respondents have been in the service for 10 years and above with 30 percent for 20-29 years, 28 percent for 10-19 years and 24 percent of 30 years and above and the remaining percentage have been in the service for 9 years and below. In terms of position title, most of the respondents are in Teacher I, II and III positions. With regards to the subjects handled, some teachers are teaching more than 1 subject.

The Level of Effectiveness of Values Integration in Teaching the Different Subjects

Table 2 presents the computed weighted mean on the level of effectiveness of values integration in teaching the different subjects with respect to classroom management.

Table 2
Computed Weighted Mean on the Level of Effectiveness of Values Integration in Teaching the Different Subjects with Respect to Classroom Management

Classroom Management The Teacher...	$W\bar{x}$	VI	Rank
1. Practices punctuality and finishes tasks on time.	3.51	VE	10
2. Devotes time to work and does things in an orderly manner	3.82	VE	8
3. Praises students and gives rewards on accomplishments.	4.01	VE	7
4. Presents challenging learning tasks.	4.13	VE	5
5. Responds to and provides learning activities for students according to growth and behavioral developments levels.	4.06	VE	6
6. Maintains order and discipline in the classroom.	4.15	VE	4
7. Shows interest in students' problems and needs.	4.23	VE	3
8. Gives constructive criticism on students.	4.43	VE	2
9. Makes oneself available to students for assistance.	4.52	VME	1
10. Help develop self confidence among students.	3.68	VE	9
OVERALL $W\bar{x}$	4.05	VE	

Legend VME - Very Much Effective

VE- Very Effective

E-Effective

As reflected from the table, with respect to classroom management, the overall weighted mean obtained is 4.05 interpreted Very Effective. Among the items, first in rank is "makes oneself available to students for assistance" with weighted mean of 4.52 interpreted Very Much Effective. All other items are interpreted Very Effective with the last in rank is "Practice punctuality and finishes tasks on time" with a weighted mean of 3.51. The table indicates that the teachers manage their student's behavior in the classroom for an effective teaching learning process. This implies that teachers apply values integration in teaching the different subjects through effective classroom management.

Table 3 presents the computed weighted mean on the level of effectiveness of values integration in teaching the different subjects with respect to delivery of lesson.

Table 3
Computed Weighted Mean on the Level of Effectiveness of Values Integration in Teaching the Different Subjects with Respect to Delivery of Lesson

Delivery of Lesson The Teacher...	W\bar{x}	VI	Rank
1. Presents the lesson accurately and systematically	4.04	VE	9
2. Exhibits thorough and broad knowledge of lesson	4.13	VE	4
3.shows awareness of current issues/concern in his/her field	4.06	VE	7
4.relates the lesson with other areas of knowledge and community affairs	4.12	VE	5
5.integrates values formation in the lesson	4.27	VE	1
6.exhibits mastery of the lesson and enthusiasm in teaching	4.11	VE	6
7.presents ideas/concepts clearly and convincingly	3.81	VE	10
8.gives comprehensive explanation	4.05	VE	8
9.provides a variety of learning activity	4.22	VE	2
10.presents lesson logically.	4.17	VE	3
OVERALL W\bar{x}	4.10	VE	

As reflected in table 3, with respect to delivery of lesson, all items are interpreted Very Effective with an overall weighted mean of 4.10. First in rank is integrates values formation in the lesson” with weighed mean of 4.27. Last in rank is “presents ideas/concepts clearly and convincingly” with a weighted mean of 3.81. The results suggest that teachers believe that values integration in the delivery of lessons is very effective in the teaching-learning process. This implies that teachers see to it that in the daily routine, values integration in teaching the different subjects is done.

Table 4 presents the computed weighted mean on the level of effectiveness of values integration in teaching the different subjects with respect to learning application.

Table 4
Computed Weighted Mean on the Level of Values integration in Teaching Different Subjects with Respect to Learning Application

Learning ApplicationThe Teacher...	W\bar{x}	VI	Rank
1.adjusts the activities to the learning capacities, interests and comprehension to students	3.79	VE	9
2.uses different methods and techniques of teaching, adjusting them to the degrees of physical and mental growth of the students and to the lesson.	4.11	VE	6
3.teaches in an interesting manner with comprehensive explanation	4.01	VE	8
4.accepts students` comments for further discussion and analysis even when the point of view is different	4.13	VE	5
5.recognizes the principle of individual differences.	4.09	VE	7

6.utilizes varied strategies in presenting lessons	4.16	VE	4
7.utilizes educational technology in teaching	3.71	VE	10
8.provides differentiated activities for learners	4.68	VME	1
9.provides remediation activities to slow learners	4.38	VE	3
10.modifies teaching procedures when necessary	4.41	VE	2
OVERALL \bar{Wx}	4.15	VE	

As shown in table 4, with respect to learning application, the overall weighted mean is 4.15 interpreted Very Effective. First in rank is “provides differentiated activities for learners” with a weighted mean of 4.68 interpreted very Much Effective. All other items are interpreted Very Effective with last in rank is “utilizes educational technology in teaching” with a weighted mean of 3.71. The data reveal that in teaching the different subjects, values integration is emphasized in the application of learning. This implies that values developed among students are applied in their day-to-day activities.

Table 5 presents the computed weighted mean on the level of effectiveness of values integration in teaching different subjects with respect to learning assessment.

Table 5
Computed Weighted Mean on the Level of Effectiveness of Values Integration in Teaching the Different Subjects with Respect to Learning Assessment

Learning Assessment The Teacher...	\bar{Wx}	VI	Rank
1.define aims to be accomplished and holds his class responsible for their accomplishment	4.03	VE	3
2.gives remedial measures for learners to attain the desired level of learning	4.01	VE	4
3.analyzes errors/weaknesses of students	3.83	VE	5
4.asks and distributes questions that call for different levels of thinking	3.76	VE	7
5.uses modern instructional devices to make the lesson more interesting	3.68	VE	8
6. Utilizes the blackboard to explain further the lesson	3.78	VE	6
7.presents lesson using the appropriate instructional materials	3.01	E	10
8.conducts the class in a conducive atmosphere which encourages students to participate actively in the class discussion.	4.13	VE	2
9.uses appropriate language frequently	3.16	VE	9
10.uses illustrations to stipulate interest to the lesson.	4.19	VE	1
OVERALL \bar{Wx}	3.76	VE	

Table 5 depicts that with respect to learning assessment, the overall weighted mean obtained is 3.76 interpreted Very Effective. First in Rank is “uses illustrations to stipulate interest to the lesson.”

interest to the lesson.” with a weighted mean of 4.19 interpreted Very Effective while “presents lesson using the appropriate instructional materials”, with a weighted mean of 3.01 interpreted Effective. Findings indicate that in the assessment of student`s learning, values integration is being applied. This implies that in the evaluation of student`s learning, values development among the learners is taken into consideration.

Table 6 presents the computed weighted mean on the level of effectiveness of values integration in teaching the different subjects with respect to personal traits.

Table 6
Computed Weighted Mean on the Level of Effectiveness of Values Integration in Teaching the Different Subjects with Respect to Personal Traits

Personal Traits The Teacher...	$W\bar{X}$	VI	Rank
1.controls and manages emotions effectively	3.83	VE	6
2.shows patience in managing students behavior	4.09	VE	4
3.manifests positive attitudes towards constructive comments, suggestions and recommendations	3.62	VE	8
4.shows sensitivity to other`s feelings and emotions	4.13	VE	3
5.lets feeling lead to healthy choices and happiness	3.01	E	10
6.stays calm in emergency situation	3.74	VE	7
7.Does not get angry easily	3.84	VE	5
8.understands feeling of individuals	3.14	E	9
9.exhibits good temper	4.26	VE	1
1. Shows consideration to students	4.17	VE	2
OVERALL $W\bar{X}$	3.78	VE	

Table 6 depicts that with respect to personal traits, the overall weighted mean is 3.78 interpreted Very Effective. Eight out ten items are interpreted Very Effective with first in rank is “exhibits good temper”, with a weighted mean of 4.26. Two items interpreted as Effective with last in rank is” Let`s feeling lead to healthy choices and happiness”, with a weighted mean of 3.01. The findings reveal that teachers possess the necessary desirable traits as teachers. This implies that they serve as role models to their students in values development.

Table 7 presents the composite table on the level of values integration in teaching the different subject.

Table 7

Composite Table on the Level of Values Integration in Teaching the Different Subjects.

Aspects	$W\bar{x}$	VI	Rank
Classroom Management	4.05	VE	3
Delivery of Lesson	4.10	VE	2
Learning of Application	4.15	VE	1
Learning Assessment	3.76	VE	5
Personal Traits	3.78	VE	4
OVERALL $W\bar{x}$	3.97	VE	

As shown in table 7, the composite weighted mean obtained is 3.97 interpreted Very Effective. Among the aspects, first in rank is “Learning of Application” with an overall weighted mean of 4.15 interpreted Very Effective. All the other aspects are interpreted Very Effective with last in rank is “Learning Assessment”, with a weighted mean of 3.76. It could be deduced from the results that integration of values in teaching different subjects is very effective as perceived by-teachers. This implies that teachers play a great part in the values development among students.

The Significant Difference on the Perception of the Respondents on the Level of Effectiveness of Values Integration in Teaching the Different Subjects with Respect to the Different Aspects in Terms of their Profile

Table 8 presents the computed F-values on the perception of the respondents on the level of effectiveness of values integration in teaching the different subjects with respect to the different aspects in terms of their profile.

Table 8

Computed F-values on the Perception of the Respondents on the Level of Effectiveness of Values Integration in Teaching the Different Subjects With Respect to the Different Aspects in Terms of their Profile

Age	Fcomp	P-value	Ho	VI
Classroom Management	3.76	.001	Rejected	Significant
Delivery of Lesson	3.08	.018	Rejected	Significant
Learning Application	3.12	.022	Rejected	Significant
Learning Assessment	3.98	.007	Rejected	Significant
Personal Traits	3.35	.004	Rejected	Significant
Sex	Fcomp	P-value	Ho	VI
Classroom Management	.16	.342	Accepted	Not Significant

Delivery of Lesson	.72	.282	Accepted	Not Significant
Learning Application	.98	.963	Accepted	Not Significant
Learning Assessment	.92	.738	Accepted	Not Significant
Personal Traits	1.07	.244	Accepted	Not Significant
Educational Attainment	Fcomp	P-value	Ho	VI
Classroom Management	1.42	.148	Accepted	Not Significant
Delivery of Lesson	1.01	.979	Accepted	Not Significant
Learning Application	1.42	.093	Accepted	Not Significant
Learning Assessment	1.72	.074	Accepted	Not Significant
Personal Traits	1.05	.323	Accepted	Not Significant
Length of Service	Fcomp	P-value	Ho	VI
Classroom Management	3.67	.006	Rejected	Significant
Delivery of Lesson	4.69	.014	Rejected	Significant
Learning Application	3.96	.007	Rejected	Significant
Learning Assessment	4.48	.003	Rejected	Significant
Personal Traits	4.89	.007	Rejected	Significant
Position Title	Fcomp	P-value	Ho	VI
Classroom Management	1.58	.389	Accepted	Not Significant
Delivery of Lesson	1.39	.987	Accepted	Not Significant
Learning Application	1.79	.453	Accepted	Not Significant
Learning Assessment	1.36	.458	Accepted	Not Significant
Personal Traits	1.59	.916	Accepted	Not Significant
Subjects Handled	Fcomp	P-value	Ho	VI

Classroom Management	3.67	.006	Rejected	Significant
Delivery of Lesson	4.69	.014	Rejected	Significant
Learning Application	3.96	.007	Rejected	Significant
Learning Assessment	4.48	.003	Rejected	Significant
Personal Traits	4.89	.007	Rejected	Significant

It could be gleaned from the table that in terms of age, length of service and subjects handles, the computed F-values in all aspects obtained probability values less than .05. This rejects the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference on the perception of the teacher -respondents on the level of effectiveness of values integration in teaching the different subjects in terms of age, length of service and subjects handled. On the contrary, in terms of sex, educational attainment and position title, the null hypothesis is accepted since all aspects, the probability values are greater than .05. Findings indicate that sex, educational attainment and position title have no bearing on the teacher's perception regarding values integration. Findings imply that teachers age, length of service and subjects handled are significant in their perception on values integration.

Summary

Based on the analysis and interpretation of data most of the teacher respondents are females with ages 31 years old and above pursuing graduate education and have been in the service for 15 years and above. Some of them are handling one or more subjects.

Values Integration in teaching the different subject is very effective with respect to classroom management, delivery of lesson, learning application, learning assessment and personal traits. In terms of sex, educational attainment and position title the null hypothesis as accepted while in terms of age, length of service and subjects handled, the null hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusions

Based on the study it can be concluded that perception of the teacher -respondents on the level of effectiveness of values integration in teaching the different subjects differ significantly in terms of age, length of service and subjects handled. On the other hand, sex, educational attainment and position title are not significant.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn the following recommendations offered:

1. Values integration in teaching the different subjects in secondary schools should be strengthened for better student development.
2. Students should be exposed to a variety of activities that will enhance their values development.
3. The proposed action plan is recommended for implementation
4. Further studies considering other variables may be conducted

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This is a declaration by the author/s in his/their own words and in paragraph form which includes compliance with obtaining informed consent, the respondents' freedom to withdraw from the study at any time, anonymity of the respondents was maintained, the respondents' well-being was safeguarded, no conflict of interest exists in the conduct of the study, plagiarism was strictly avoided, there was no bias in the interpretation of the findings and that the results were used purely for research.

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Action Plan to Enhance the Values Integration in Teaching the Different Subjects.
Based on the findings, an action plan is proposed to enhance the values integration in teaching the different subjects.

ACTION PLAN TO ENHANCE THE VALUES INTEGRATION IN TEACHING THE DIFFERENT SUBJECTS SCHOOL YEAR 2015-2016

Area Thrust	Program Activity	Objective	Manpower	Time Frame	Budget	Source of Fund	Success Indicator
Student Development	Supervision of Classes	Diagnose/assess students' progress and behavior	Teachers Students	June 2015- March 2016	P15000	Student Development Fund	Students' progress /behavior improved by 50%
	Administration of Periodical Test in ESP in all grade levels	Diagnose/assess the students through periodical test	Teachers Students	June 2015- March 2016	P40000	School operation Fund MOOE	Students' proficiency increased by 75%
	Individual Group Counselling	Raise Self-esteem-of individual students	Guidance Counselor	June 2015- March 2016	P10000	School operation Fund MOOE	Students' misbehavior decreased by 25%
Faculty Development	Scholarship Grants	Provide quality services and equal opportunities for upliftment and professional development	Teachers administrators	June 2015- March 2016	P50000	Faculty Welfare Fund	Qualified Teachers are recommended for reclassification and promotions
	Implementation of Key DepEd programs and policies pertaining to teachers' welfare and development	Upgrade knowledge/competencies of advisers and guidance advocate on the different strategies and innovations in guidance counseling	Principal Teachers Guidance	June 2015- March 2016	P50000	School operation Fund MOOE	Teachers upgraded competencies increased by 75%
Curriculum Development	Utilization of different teaching technique	Enrich the values education curriculum to facilitate learning	Administrators Subject Area Chairperson	June 2015	P5000	School Fund	75% of the needed instructional materials developed
	Curriculum Enrichment and Modification	Enrich curriculum guides	Teachers Administrators Subject Area Chairperson	April to May 2016	P10000	School operation Fund MOOE	100% of curriculum guides in different subjects modified
	Enrichment utilization and monitoring of instructional materials	Develop a low-cost instructional material that is effective and applicable to the needs of the students	Teachers	June 2015	P10000	School operation Fund MOOE	75% of the needed instructional materials developed
Physical Facilities Development	Maintenance of Physical facilities	Provide an audio-visual room for students	Administrators Teachers	April 2016	P100000	School operation Fund MOOE	Classrooms and buildings repaired and maintained

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